

PANPOC

A reliable and fluorescence-based instrument for ultra-rapid diagnosis.

It is an instrument with integrated heater and optical detection systems. Its pioneering technology builds on a real-time fluorescence-based detection which can be used for both clinical diagnostics (human samples) and veterinary surveillance.

The aim is to provide health authorities, veterinary and clinical end-users, as well as primary care providers, with a reliable portable fluorescence-based point-of-care instrument for fast highly-accurate RNA respiratory virus detection.

CONSORTIUM

PAIR

Pandemic information to support rapid response

PAIR

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THE PROJECT

Most epidemics have been caused by RNA respiratory viruses that often originate from animals to find new hosts in humans under specific environmental conditions.

PAIR is an EU project to develop rapid and reliable detection methods for respiratory RNA viruses and foster pandemic preparedness.

IMPACTS

Science
& Technology

Policy

Society

Industry

New guidelines for a European **One Health genomic-informed surveillance and outbreak response** will be issued, based on data and information collected through PAIR tools.

TECHNOLOGIES

PAIR project will develop two ambitious technologies to provide veterinary, clinical end-users, primary care providers, health authorities with rapid RNA respiratory virus detection methods and reliable digital models for pandemic rapid response.

PANRISK

An accurate and reliable platform for epidemiologic prediction and prevention. It is a platform with two models:

PANRISK SPILLOVER MODEL

to monitor animal pathogenic viruses and genomic variation, predict human infection and the cross-border risk of spillover.

PANRISK EPIDEMIOLOGIC MODEL

to monitor when viruses exceed appropriate thresholds based on test data.

It aims to trace epidemic trajectories, ecological interactions and spatial-temporal patterns. This enables an alarm in case of pandemic risk.